

A Study on Minimum Wage Comparisons in the World, Especially in Developing Countries

Assoc. Prof. Osman Doruk

Dokuz Eylul University Lecturer

Certified Public Accountant - Independent Auditor

St Clements University Associate Professor of Business

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Abstract

The impact of the minimum wage on labor and goods markets continues to be a topic of constant interest to economists and policymakers and supplies fertile ground for academic research. More than nine hundred studies on the minimum wage were published between 2000 and 2020, and the number of these studies has increased since then. In contrast to earlier research on the minimum wage, which was mostly conducted using univariate time-series techniques, the current empirical work is notable for its wide variety of methodologies, data sources, and measurement standards. When the "New Minimum Wage Survey" (NMWR) was launched in the early 1990s, the problem

of deciding the effects of the minimum wage resulted in the development of new methods. Methods such as panel data analysis and quasi-experiments are included in this category. More recently, the use of synthetic control methods has entered this literature. (“What Does the Minimum Wage Do in Developing Countries? A Review of ...”) (“What Does the Minimum Wage Do in Developing Countries? A Review of ...”) There has also been an expansion in the types of outcomes considered in the minimum wage study. While the employment implications of the minimum wage remain the focus of contemporary research, there has been an increasing emphasis on other employment-related effects. These include hours worked, attendances and departures, unemployment and vacancies, the impact on working in a second job or a part-time job, as well as the division of labor between the formal and informal sectors. There is also a greater focus on effects on wages and earnings, with special emphasis on distinguishing between effects on workers who should earn the minimum wage and spillover effects on workers who previously earned more. More than the new minimum wage Some research has been done on the effects of increased business volume as well as health care and receiving a pension, looking at the effects of the minimum wage on schooling and education, as well as on family income. In addition, studies have been conducted examining the effects of the minimum wage on the receipt of health and pensions.

Keywords: *Minimum Wage, Remuneration of Employees, Minimum Subsistence, Minimum Wage in the World*

1. Introduction

There has been a significant amount of new research on the consequences of price changes, particularly price changes in food and beverage businesses. In addition to considering a wider variety of potentially affected communities, these more diverse approaches and outcomes include these communities as well. Most of the studies were adolescents and young adults; however, recent research has shifted their focus to examining the effects on those with lower levels of education, men and women, different racial and ethnic groups, specific industries, full-time and part-time workers, and households. Most minimum wage studies have been done in OECD member

countries; however, a sizable body of research on less developed countries are beginning to emerge.

2. Improving Working Conditions of Low-Income Employees

The effects of the minimum wage are of particular importance for these countries as they face greater challenges both in improving the working conditions of low-income workers and in increasing the number of paid jobs available. A few papers have done an excellent job of summarizing estimates from numerous studies conducted in developing and low-income countries; however, no studies to date have specifically evaluated the methodology used in these studies.

Recent reviews of the literature, Nataraj , S. F Perez-Arce & KB Kumar, "The Impact of Labor Market Regulation on Employment in Low-Income Country: A Meta-Analysis", Journal of Economic Surveys, (2014), Vol. 28, Issue 3, pages 551-572; Broecke, S. , A. Forti, and M Vandeweyer, "The Impact of the Minimum Wage on Employment in Developing Economies: A Because of the importance of these issues for developing countries, a deeper understanding of the lessons learned can be enumerated.

It is necessary to make productive use of this research over the past two decades. The difficulties surrounding the technique in minimum wage research are the main subject of this study. There is also particular emphasis on measurement of results and minimum wage, as well as empirical approaches. First, we will provide an overview of the metrics and techniques to use, and then move on to a discussion of the challenges surrounding identification, the accuracy of hypothesis testing, and the differences between static and dynamic models. In the second part of this article, we review the research literature on the minimum wage in developing countries, focusing on the criteria and methodologies used in the published studies.

While some of these studies are methodologically advanced, they do not always use the newest approaches and in other cases use methods that were considered problematic in the past (Belman & Wolfson, 2014). These methodological issues are not unique to research in poor countries. This

approach can be helpful in ensuring that estimates are methodologically sound and in providing guidance in the process of designing policies for developing countries.

3. Various Models and Sizes

Before moving on to a discussion of the dependent variables and measures of the minimum wage, we begin our overview of models and measures by discussing many of the most common models used to estimate equations. The "Canonical Model" typically involves using panel data models to estimate the effects of a minimum wage increase. This can be done either by aggregating the data into "state" by year observations, or by using repeated cross-sectional data on individuals with "status" and year variables in the data. However, estimation of panel data models is by far the most common method. This structure was first used by Neumark and Wascher (1992) in their minimum wage research. Allows the inclusion of state and year fixed effect dummies that can consider state invariant year effects as well as time invariant state effects. Therefore, there is less need for complex controls for variables other than the minimum wage that may affect the variable being controlled. The structure of this model, now referred to as the "canonical model", looks like this: To be more precise, the geographic unit can be any administrative unit responsible for setting its own minimum wage. This could be a state, province, territory, or county, among other designations for an administrative unit, depending on the country in question.

In most cases, these models use an employment measure, such as the employment to population ratio, as the dependent variable. Earnings and various measures of school enrollment are two other examples of dependent variables investigated using similar panel data frames. There are many ways to quantify the minimum wage, but the most common ways are to use a Kaitz rate, true minimum wage, or relative minimum wage measure. Discussing the variables examines each of these measures in more detail . The sum of the control variables is typically quite small, as it is often predicted that the fixed effects will explain most of the factors that will affect the dependent variable. For example, Neumark (2001) calculated the criteria for his analysis of the response of adolescent employment. These specifications simply included the prime-age male unemployment rate, the prime-age skilled male employment rate, and the youth population ratio. Within the scope

of this research, the assumption that few factors other than the minimum wage fluctuate with both time and place has emerged as a matter of increasing concern. We address this issue further in the context of our discussion of identification. The early assumption that there is an error term meaning independent and identically distributed has also been shown to be problematic, with implications for the correct calculation of standard errors and testing of hypotheses.

4. Quasi-Experiments

The creation of quasi-experiments is the other dominant strategy in this research group and has been used extensively (QEs). The detailed characterization of the experimental and control groups is what distinguishes qualitative experiments from other types of research (most studies use some form of regression) rather than the methodologies used to conduct the research. For example, Card's initial study of fast-food restaurants used before and after data on the same set of establishments to measure the employment impact of minimum wage increases. The control for the post-employment change level was the individual's previous work in an organization and was used in both pre- and post-employment datasets. This method has evolved into studies utilizing businesses in nearby administrative units, only one of which has implemented a minimum wage increase, to assess the impact of the minimum wage on employment. These studies were conducted to determine the effect of the minimum wage. These studies, such as those by Card and Krueger (1994) and Allegretto, Dube and Reich (2011) compare the change in employment levels – employment after the increase minus employment before it – in countries that raise the minimum wage. It is the simultaneous change in nearby jurisdictions with no increase in the minimum wage. Specifically, they look at the difference between employment after the increase and employment before it.

Working Conditions and Employment Series No. The methodologies and procedures used in sixty-two research are more diverse than those used in classical studies; however, these studies are recognizable by the attention paid to the definition of comparison groups.

5. Most Important Factors

Minimum Wage and Related Measures of Success Although there has been a significant increase in the breadth of research on the effects of the minimum wage in OECD countries, this trend has not been as pronounced as in studies in developing countries. . With a few notable exceptions, research on these countries has mostly focused on employment-related issues. As a result, we will begin our discussion by focusing on the dependent factors that influence employment outcomes. After evaluating the employment issue, we will move on to measures related to wages and earnings and minimum wage. In examining these challenges with data and variable creation, we build heavily on our previous understanding of labor market data in the United States. Data from other nations will each have their own unique characteristics that researchers should consider when developing metrics to use with that data.

6. Variables Used to Measure Employment

There are several different methods by which employment is evaluated. Whether the measure relates to the entire amount of wage (employed) labor, normally measured in hours, or to more rough measures, such as the number of workers, determines the finesse of the measure. The latter will be our primary focus for the time being due to the prevalence of research using it.

7. Initial Predictions of Job Openings and Closings

The employment rate is a statistic that is used more often than any other metric in demographic research. This is the proportion of the population actively participating in the workforce, for example, single women, married women, or young adults. The proportion of young people who state that they are working is called the youth employment rate. In the authorized model that classifies data by status and year, the answer would be the typical percentage of adolescents working in status I in the specified year t. If at some point in time every adolescent reported that they had a job, the proportion of employed youth would equal one. It would equal zero if no one reported having a job, but it would equal fifty percent if at least half had a job. Research using it

implicitly assumes that a fixed proportion of young people will always be employed, even if there are no trends and nothing changes but the size of the youth population. This is because it automatically corrects for changes in younger population size, and studies using it implicitly assume this.

Other typical measures of employment outcomes, such as the unemployment rate, are only occasionally used in minimum wage surveys. A person is considered unemployed according to international standards if he is neither employed nor self-employed but is both ready to work and trying to find a job. The unemployment rate is calculated by dividing the number of unemployed people by the total number of people working or looking for a job. The distinction between those who are unemployed and those who are not actively looking for work is sensitive to influences such as the current state of the labor market, availability of unemployment benefits, and whether participants are enrolled in school. This poses a challenge for minimum wage studies because it makes a distinction between the unemployed and those who are not actively looking for work (full-time students are not classified as unemployed).

Compared to the already complex effort to determine how the minimum wage affects employment rates, it is much more difficult to isolate the impact of the minimum wage from the influence of other variables that affect the unemployment rate.

Other types of research that make use of organizational data, as well as specific industries in the Working Conditions and Employment Studies series, assess employment by either the number of jobs (or the number of people employed) or employment. When performing these "quasi-experiments" the observation unit will be a commercial establishment, such as a fast-food restaurant, and the interest variable will be the number of employments available at each firm before and after the minimum wage. In most cases, when conducting regression studies on the restaurant business, researchers will use either the total employment in the industry or the growth rate of the number of employees in the industry.

8. Timekeeping Units and Measures

Many employment indicators are simplistic as they do not distinguish between full-time and part-time jobs and do not consider the varying lengths of the work week. Some people have argued that considering the controversy surrounding employment's response to the minimum wage, more nuanced approaches may offer a solution. These are usually differences in the number of paid hours an employee must work. A typical option is to use the total number of hours worked for an individual, an institution or organization, or the industry. Other metrics include the average working hours of all employees in a company or industry, as well as full-time equivalents, or FTEs, which are the total number of hours worked divided by the number of hours considered to be in a job. "Working hours" derived from organizational statistics are based on actual hours paid in each time, most typically a given week. This is when data is collected from weekly totals. It is common for surveys of demographic groups (often based on household surveys) to include a range of different measures of hours worked. It is possible to take measurements of both actual hours worked in each time and typical hours worked. Studies using regular clocks will not be fully comparable to studies using real clocks, as they evaluate closely related but different phenomena. This is especially true if, like some surveys, typical hours for people with variable working hours are labeled with a qualitative result.

9. Marginal Productivity

employees are not paid less than what is considered their "marginal productivity" (Eurofound 2018); this is something that can happen if workers have minimal leverage to bargain. Therefore, given that unionization increases workers' negotiating power, it should come as no surprise that some countries with solid social security and strong unions do not have minimum wages. They are less dependent on an institutionalized minimum wage, as they do not have to settle for low-paying employment because they have alternative opportunities. However, if the minimum wage is raised above the productivity of the least productive employees, companies may choose not to employ them. Thus, a high minimum wage may reduce the practicality of hiring unproductive people in the workplace. This, in turn, results in a loss in employment of these individuals, leading to a decrease in the competitiveness of producers in the corresponding geographic area (Neumark and

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Wascher 2006). Evaluating the effects of minimum wage policy requires academics around the world to try to estimate the real-world effects of minimum wages. This is vital in assessing the effects of the minimum wage policy. Impacts on employment is the most used standard as a measuring stick; it has been found that in most cases, employment falls after the introduction of the minimum wage (Neumark and Wascher 2006). Numerous studies have shown an improvement in productivity that compensates for the detrimental effects on competitiveness (International Labor Organization 2018). Additionally, Picl and Richter (2014) and other researchers found that a higher than subsistence minimum wage increase can encourage individuals to join the labor market. The recent implementation of the minimum wage in Germany in 2015 was analyzed by Bossler and Greiner (2016), who concluded that there was a moderate increase in the average wage (+4.8%) and a small decrease in employment (-1.9. %), respectively, these calculations are envisaged for jobs that are paid less than the newly applied minimum wage . Despite this, the proportion of affected workers was less than ten percent. There appears to be a consensus that setting the minimum wage at a moderately elevated level is socially beneficial as the risk of poverty is reduced and the labor supply increases but setting the minimum wage at a significantly higher level is socially beneficial. It is harmful because of its negative effects on employment and productivity. According to Eurofound (2018), a more comprehensive review of the effects of the minimum wage on earnings, productivity, employment, and other aspects is provided. Throughout this article, we define the statutory minimum wage as the minimum amount of financial reward a worker receives for a specified period of work as determined by the (central) government and applicable to all geographic jurisdictions and most workers. Because there is no single official definition of the minimum wage, we define the statutory minimum wage as the minimum amount of financial reward a worker receives for working for a certain period. If there is not going to be a standard definition and regulation of the minimum wage, it should be written into the labor legislation of each nation. Some countries have an industry-specific de facto minimum wage level, but this level is not considered "legal" as it results in collective bargaining agreements rather than being set by central government. In the following sections, we will provide a descriptive overview of minimum wages worldwide, with emphasis on Europe and a few additional countries to choose from. To begin, we will consider the history and prevalence of (legal) minimum wages, the

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(relative) minimum wage level, as well as short-term trends in minimum wage levels that are important to countries.

There is a significant disparity in the amount of money that makes up the euro equivalent of the monthly minimum wage, ranging from sixty-seven euros in the Indian state of Bihar to 3069 euros in the Swiss cantons of Neuchâtel and Jura. Adjusted to reflect costs at the level typical for the EU-28, this inequality is reduced: 215 euros in Bihar and 2,177 euros in Neuchâtel and Jura. Even when expressed as a percentage of average wage, inequalities are significant. On the other hand, some countries stand out on both ends of this relative measure: in the United States, the minimum wage is only 34% of the average wage, while in Turkey it reaches 74% of the average wage. Greece (which fell in absolute terms in 2012 as a direct result of the economic crisis) and the United States (2009, but some states have adjusted their minimum levels). However, comparisons between countries are difficult for several varied reasons. The following are the pre-tax amounts: It is possible for two nations to have quite various levels of discretionary family income while having the same minimum wage. The use of multiple time units makes it difficult to compare the figures in a meaningful way. This is because working hours, national holidays and paid leave days all vary. Therefore, minimum wages in developing countries may appear higher than they really are because workers in poor countries may need to work longer hours than those in rich countries. On the other hand, the monthly wage is a better indicator of how much an employee can earn overall, because in most industrialized countries an employee cannot be compensated for working more than 40 hours a week. As a result, we provide the numbers using the monthly format. In addition, many countries introduce exemptions from minimum wage requirements for certain industries, youth and (inexperienced) workers.

Most age exemptions are structured so that young workers do not earn the full minimum wage, but instead receive a percentage of the minimum wage based on their age. This is the case because age exceptions are set up that way. For example, in Australia, workers under the age of sixteen earn 36.8% of the minimum wage, workers aged sixteen receive 47.3% of the minimum wage, workers aged seventeen earn 57.8% and workers aged eighteen earn 68.3%. takes its name. In 2018, workers aged nineteen receive 82.5% of the minimum wage, and workers aged twenty receive

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97.7% of the minimum wage. (mywage.org 2018). Various countries have a different minimum wage rate for workers currently in the training or apprenticeship stages of their careers.

For example, the minimum wage in Ireland is recalculated to consider the fact that most young workers in the country are still enrolled in school. The minimum wage is 75% of the legal fee in the first quarter, 80% in the second quarter, and 90% in the third and final quarter (a quarter must be at least one month and not more than one year). Both Luxembourg and Malta have a system where the minimum wage increases in proportion to an employee's level of education and years of experience (Eurofound 2018). Depending on the industry, the minimum wage rate can vary significantly from country to country. For example, workers receiving taxable tips in the United States are subject to various wage rates. (Year: 2018 United States of America) Workers working in public job programs (Belügyminisztérium 2018), which are programs for the unemployed or permanently job seekers in Hungary, receive a wage set separately by the government. In Hungary, this fee is known as the public job programmer fee (Eurofound 2018).

10. Ability to Work

There are exceptions for workers doing simple jobs in Japan (United States 2018). In New Zealand and Germany, employers can deduct meals and accommodation from the minimum wage, particularly for seasonal workers in the agricultural sector (Eurofound 2018; Government of New Zealand 2018a). Other features for which the minimum wage rate is set may be the disability of workers. For example, in New Zealand, a labor inspector may grant wage exemption permits to disabled workers (New Zealand Government 2018b). In Australia, adults whose productivity is affected by their disability are regulated to be paid a percentage of the national minimum wage. For example, a person whose ability to work is assessed as 70% is entitled to 70% of the corresponding pay rate (Australian Government 2018a). Other aspects that can increase the minimum wage are working late at night, early in the morning, on weekends or public holidays, as in Australia (Australian Government 2018b). -20 0 20 40 60 80 % Greece USA Slovenia Malta Netherlands Belgium Australia Luxembourg France Canada Japan Brazil New Zealand United

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Kingdom Russia Portugal Spain Croatia Hungary Poland Latvia South Korea Slovakia Czech Republic Turkey Estonia China Ireland Lithuania Romania Bulgaria

As mentioned earlier, in most countries the government has the power to set the minimum wage level. For example, in 2017 most EU member states decided on the final minimum wage, considering the recommendations of other actors or mechanisms. In contrast, in some EU member states (Czech Republic, Poland, Portugal, Romania, Slovakia and Slovenia), the government consulted with other parties, but because they could not reach an agreement, the government unilaterally decided on the minimum wage level (Eurofound 2018). Triple

In some countries, consultation takes place in tripartite bodies. These tripartite bodies normally consist of government, trade unions and employers. In 2017, most EU member states were consulted about the minimum wage level by a tripartite body. Some of the tripartite bodies made a non-binding recommendation (Eurofound 2018). However, tripartite organizations are important not only in the process of setting the minimum wage in EU member states, but also in, for example, Japan and Turkey (wageindicator.org 2018). In Turkey, the tripartite body, called the Minimum Wage Determination Committee, even sets the country's minimum wage rates, which only need to be announced by the government.

Decisions are taken by majority vote of its members (International Labor Office 2014). Independent expert committee: In some countries, for example Australia, Brazil, France or Germany, an independent expert committee is established to consult the government on the minimum wage level. In Australia, this committee is called Fair Work Australia's Minimum Wage Panel. There are five Commissioners from a variety of backgrounds, including economics, business, social justice, workplace relations, academia, and community service. Every fiscal year, Fair Work Australia's Minimum Wage Panel conducts an annual review and decides on the minimum wage level based on that review. The review considers written applications from relevant organizations and individuals, consultations before the Expert Panel, and research commissioned by the Panel. The decision is subsequently incorporated into minimum wage changes enforced by the States or the Federal Court (Australian Government 2018c). Apart from the tripartite or expert committee: Trade unions and employers' organizations can also play a key

role in setting the minimum wage level. In 2017, for example, in Bulgaria, France, Hungary, Latvia and the United Kingdom, trade unions and employers' organizations negotiated the minimum wage level independently of any tripartite or expert committee. However, trade unions and employers' organizations in Hungary and Bulgaria failed to reach a consensus on the minimum wage level in 2017 (Eurofound 2018). Indexing mechanism: Belgium, Brazil, Canada, China, India, Netherlands, Malta, and some states in Turkey normally use an indexing mechanism to set the minimum wage level. For example, in China, this indexing mechanism includes regional economic factors, including average living expenses and wages, social security contribution, unemployment rates, and level of development (wageindicator.org 2018).

11. Institutions Involved in the Process of Determining the Minimum Wage Level

However, cross-country comparisons are difficult as some countries include part-time workers earning less than or equal to the minimum wage on a monthly basis, while others do not. The OECD reports the number of workers earning less than 105% of the minimum wage in 2010 and 2014 in various countries. Cross-country statistics are partially harmonized and only count employees over twenty-one to avoid various exceptions affecting these numbers. In 2014, it ranges from 0% in Belgium (which has a medium minimum wage) to 43% in Turkey (which has a high minimum wage). High numbers may indicate distorting effects compared to the unregulated scenario (if the minimum wage is strictly enforced): while many workers were paid only the minimum wage, they may have received a lower wage in the unregulated situation. Nine countries had a share of 5% or less, suggesting that the minimum wage had little distorting effects in these countries.

All the latter countries also set their minimum wages at less than half their median wages. Eurofound (2018) has attempted to list the percentage of workers earning minimum wages from various national sources. In European countries, this rate varies between 3% and 40%. It is noteworthy that in some Eastern European countries (including Romania, Bulgaria, Estonia) the

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share of workers working near the middle wage has increased rapidly in recent years. One explanation would be the sharp increase in the minimum wage (see Figure 2). However, GDP also increased rapidly; this may have happened at the same time as changes in income distribution (due to the full admission of Romania and Bulgaria to the EU single market for free capital and labor in 2014).

Despite increasing demand for labor, there has been no significant increase in overall salary levels. One of the reasons for this is that metropolitan firms are successful in attracting workers from rural areas, thus keeping their current workforce at a healthy level (Cai 2017). Therefore, it is argued that the increase in the minimum wage is a policy of Chinese President Xi Jinping, who has committed to eradicate poverty by 2020 and is now pressing the provinces to do the same.

This is because Xi Jinping wants to eradicate poverty by 2020 and want to ensure that the minimum wage acts as a safety net (Cai 2017). However, with rising labor costs, there is a concern that many investors are choosing to move production of low-value and labor-intensive products to provinces in China or to other low-wage countries such as Vietnam. This is a concern because rising labor costs have led to an increase in labor cost (Koty 2018). With a large supply of labor at lower wages elsewhere in the world, critics worry China may lose its comparative advantage. Also, many of those who oppose raising the minimum wage argue that doing so will reduce the number of employment opportunities available for low-wage workers (Fang and Lin 2013). Despite the recent increase, it is safe to say that China still has one of the lowest minimum wage levels in the world.

In addition, the differences in the minimum wage application have been the subject of differences in terms of which groups are exempt from the minimum wage, the way the amount is determined, and the differences created by whom. Although the concept of the legal minimum wage has been around for quite some time, the controversy surrounding it continues unabated. This is true not only in countries like China that already enforce it, but also in countries like South Africa where there is a strong movement calling for a minimum wage to be established. Finally, countries like Sweden show that there are other avenues to an actual minimum wage that are still effective in achieving the same goals. This is because developing countries have lower poverty lines. Third, a considerable number of people living in poverty have jobs in the unorganized or self-employed

sectors of the economy. In addition, high inflation rates make it difficult to establish a minimum wage.

On the other hand, in the United States, wages from a minimum wage job are often not enough to lift a poor person out of poverty. Also, the general equilibrium analysis models developed by Alan Carruth and Andrew Oswald and those developed by Edward Learner show that in small open economies, rising wages in the formal sector will always result in higher wages in the informal sector. An increase in union or minimum wages in the formal sector cannot be reflected as an increase in prices, which is the basic intuition that supports this finding. As a result, profits fall, causing capital, unlike labor, to move out of the formal sector. The informal economy benefits from capital movement that increases wages and employment levels in the industry. There is also some evidence that registered and unregistered wages move together in some countries, for example Brazil, Costa Rica, and Mexico. This goes against the predictions of conventional analysis, which would lead one to expect that these two types of charges have an inverse relationship. These countries are included in this study. 10. Learner by Carruth and Oswald (1981); by Carruth and Oswald (1995). Although Carruth and Oswald designed their model to analyze the effects of labor unions, their work can also be applied to minimum wage laws.

12. Conclusion

It is important to note that the effects of minimum wage changes are not based on the existence of a non-standard link between minimum wages and employment in the sector covered by neither the Harris-Todaro model nor the demand-linked general equilibrium models. Unlike some models proposed by the "new economy" of the minimum wage (see, for example, Card and Krueger, 1995, p. 236), in these model's higher real wages in the formal sector inevitably led to lower levels. This is because higher real wages in the informal sector led to higher levels of informal employment. On the other hand, a non-standard result does not oblige low-income people to do business by paying the minimum wage. However, the assumption must be made that the government could influence the real value of the minimum wage through legislative changes in the counted minimum wage, and that the minimum wage is enforced in at least some sectors of the economy. This is a

necessary but not sufficient condition. In closed economies, covered sector wages are more likely to move inversely with wages in the non-covered sector, although the outcome will depend on the underlying parameters in the model. In open economies, covered sector wages are more likely to move in the same direction as non-covered sector wages. 12. For information on Mexico, see Maloney (1996); For details on Brazil and Costa Rica, see the World Bank; (1990, p. 110). Studies for Latin America show that there is a relationship between the increase in the minimum wage and the reduction of poverty (and poverty reduction. For example, Samuel Morley, after looking at the relationship between minimum wage and poverty in a cross section of Latin American countries, finds a negative relationship between minimum wage and poverty. Most of the econometric research currently available focuses on the link between the minimum wage and the salaries of workers with low education or training levels, although rural areas are where most people in developing countries live in poverty and where the link is all these studies have focused on urban workers. Predicting the characteristics of the labor market is another challenging task, as it requires a significant amount of data and is therefore impossible to conduct simultaneously for many countries . would be a different strategy for estimating factors leading to poverty, serving as one of the variables.

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